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METHODS OF RELATIVE ASSESSMENT / SELF-ASSESSMENT OF MARITIME AGENCY COMPANIES

МЕТОДИ ВІДНОСНОЇ ОЦІНКИ / САМООЦІНКИ МОРСЬКИХ АГЕНТСЬКИХ КОМПАНІЙ

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In recent years there has been a significant decline in the level of service in the maritime sector. This is caused not that much by increase of tariffs and decrease in the flow of goods in Ukraine as a redistribution of "freight" markets, but in hence transition of principals to other agents. Regarding this matter, it is necessary to consider activities of maritime agent, consider its rights, functions and identify possible trends in the market of maritime agency service. Conduct scientific and practical research aimed onto analyzing of status and improvement of each individual agency company, its place among its competitors.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Today there are many publications on subject of maritime agency and there aspects. It is necessary to mention latest works of such researchers as B. Burkinsky, A. Demyanchenko, A. Kibik, A. Tselovalnikov, A. Filippenko and many others who studied market, economic, legal and business aspects of the activity of sea ports and en-terprises working in the near transport- maritime sector. Among researchers of this problems of activity of mari-time agencies, it is necessary to separately mention scientific theseses of V. Vyhovsky, I. Petrov, N. Sergeeva, O. Poltavsky, D. Popov, as well as journalistic publications (in specialized editions) by A. Bronetsky, I. Lander, N. Miroshnichenko, V. Selivanova, O. Chebotarenko and others. Basing on all previous publications, we can state that there was made complete market analysis for further work and the identification of trends on it.

The aim of the article is to consider a number of criteria for already existing shipping companies of Ukraine and in the world for further identification of the most effective methods of valuation / self-assessment of companies of this type.

The main part

Transport industry is an important link in each national economy, which has function of communication be-tween different sectors of production and economic complex with national

Ярмолович Д.Ю. Методи відносної оцінки / самооцінки морських агентських компаній. Науково-методична стаття.

Статтю присвячено дослідженню діяльності морських агентів, як на Україні, так и по всьо-му світі. Розглянуто можливі критерії оцінки та були виявлені основні з них, спираючись на котрі можна провести оцінку компанії та отримати повну картину поточного стану морської агентської компанії, її місця на ринку відносно конкурентів, спрогнозувати її можливі напрямки розвитку та багато іншого що при відповідному використанні керівництвом може сприяти гармонічному розвитку компанії. При розробці данного методу були використані данні міжнародних та національні агентських компаній.

Ключові слова: морське агентування, діяльність морських портів, торгове судноплавство, чинники оцінки, контрагенти морського агента, ефективності діяльності компанії

Iarmolovych D.Yu. Methods of relative assessment / self-assessment of maritime agency companies. Scientific and methodical article.

Article is devoted to study of the activities of marine agents, both in Ukraine and throughout the world. Possible evaluation criteria were considered and main ones were identified, based on which one can as-sess the company and get a complete picture of current state of the marine agency company, its place in the market relative to its competitors, to foresee its possible development directions and much more that can be promoted by management if appropriately used. harmonious development of the company. In developing this method, data from international and national agency companies was used.

Keywords: marine agency, seaport activity, merchant shipping, factor assessments, maritime agent contrac-tors, company efficiency

economies of other countries. For Ukraine, where one of the most important tasks is to integrate the country's economy into European structures, it should be paid extra attention to the organization of mutually beneficial cooperation with European partners, raising of standards of production and service to a competitive European level. For successful development of our country, it is important to harmoniously develop all types of transport and related services.

Maritime transport is carried out by shipping companies, as points of departure and destination serve ports where cargo is loaded and unloaded, and in addition, additional measures are implemented – storage, packaging, consolidation, etc. It can be said that shipping companies and ports act as main participants in the maritime transport process, which can not be realized without implementation of a number of additional and auxiliary operations. Latter mentioned are provided by many companies, which sometimes combine one term – "transport service". Accordingly, in market of maritime transport services as suppliers of various services are:

↓ shipping companies;
 ↓ ports;
 ↓ transport service companies (freight forwarding, agency, supply (shipbuilding) companies, companies – freight brokers, etc.).

Shipping companies and ports implement directly course of cargo delivery (transportation, transshipment, storage). Enterprises of maritime transport service can be logically divided into two groups:

↓ intermediaries (ie, connecting links in the chain of relationships) – freight forwarders, ship

agents, freight brokers, ship management companies, customs brokers;

↓ auxiliary service (supply, repair, maintenance, etc.), that is, those enterprises that do not directly participate in the processes of organization and delivery of delivery.

Therefore, by implication maritime agency is one of the most important services provided in the field of merchant shipping, to maximize efficiency ship owners of these operations use the services of maritime agents. A maritime agent acts in accordance with the order of the ship-owner, in his interests and on his behalf. The agent ensures the entry of ship-owner into official relations with cargo owners, stevedoring companies, organizations related to the servicing of vessels at the port.

Maritime transport cannot exist without the infrastructure of maritime agencies companies. But, despite rapid growth in the number of agency companies in Ukrainian ports, the quality of services provided is often still low enough, due to the following main reasons:

1. The low level of qualification of agents, as a result of which the agents cannot cope with the amount of work assigned to them.
2. The low competitiveness of agency companies can be seen through usage of a physically and morally outdated system of work. Weakly use of the latest information technologies in agent company management systems, allowing not only timely receipt and processing of information, but also to develop on the basis of its optimal management decisions [2].

The main components of the economic interest of agency companies is the increase in profits due to the components in tab. 1.

Table 1. Components of economic interest

Component of economic interest	Method of profit increasing
Expanding its market activities	Displacement of competitors at the local level (domestic)
Expansion of the market of activity	Penetration into new maritime agency markets (directly creating affiliates, affiliated companies in neighboring ports or countries)
Expansion of the market of activity	Drawing up of contracts by providing agency or participation in transnational agency companies
Eliminating competitors from your own terminal or port	The struggle for the status of a terminal agent or a monopoly port agent, in recent years has become most effective and so called popular
Establishing a trust relationship with the port administration, suppliers,	Be able to provide guaranty in difficult situations for thirist parties
Encouraging more shipowners to cooperate	Increase the client base and status of a trusted agent
Support (consulting, information) of national traders is planning to engage in maritime transport	Getting back supportand expanding the customer base

Source: own elaboration

Marine agency companies are completely independent of any single algorithm for organization and organization of services for ship-owner, captain or other customer. The main problem of all companies with self-management is the difficulty of self-analysis of the activities and results of the company's management.

Self-assessment / evaluation is a comprehensive, systematic and regular analysis of the level of activity and results of this activity. Under the method of relative self-assessment / assessment refers to analysis of management and life of each aspect of the company under consideration. Proceeding from purpose, tasks, volume and content of performed

works and services provided, set of applied functions of self-government is expressed through appropriate quantitative or qualitative coefficients, and employees as the starting point for self-assessment / evaluation. The main contributor in process of self-assessment / assessment of level of self-government and the existence of a marine agent company is agency itself. Executable functions determine complex of properties and characteristics that can be described through functions of the system of corresponding coefficients. When assessing the level of self-government it is necessary to limit the number of functions and, therefore, the factors choosing the most significant affecting the effectiveness of the company. It depends on type of activity and stage of life cycle of

the company, which is subject to self-assessment / evaluation, and other factors. As practice shows, their number should not exceed 15-20 pieces.

Method of relative estimation of a marine agency company is based on fact that at first each of the selected coefficients of analogue is established their numerical value, then actual value of numerical value of coefficients of evaluated company is determined. This assessment can be performed both by the company itself and by the involved individuals or companies; same may also be in case for an expert appraisal. The only unit of measurement of the magnitude of the selected coefficients is the points. It is advisable to be guided by the option given in tab. 2.

Table 2. Qualitative evaluation coefficients

Qualitative estimation of coefficient	Assessment factor in points
Excellent, "ideal" value	5
Good	4
Satisfactory	3
Minimum permissible	2
Unsatisfactory	1

Source: own elaboration

The ball scoring system helps both agency itself and other participants in process of evaluation, to compare the result with selected analogue of the "ideal" company and to compare level of self-management of investi-gated maritime agency company. As for self-assessment / assessment of the level of self-management of com-pany's life functions by self-government, expressed through appropriate coefficients, the proposed is determined by following formula:

$$P_{rel} = \frac{t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_n}{\sum t_k} = \frac{\frac{t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_n}{n}}{\frac{\sum t_k}{n}} = \frac{\bar{t}}{t_k}, \quad (1)$$

P_{rel} – relative self-esteem / self-management assessment of the company;

$t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n$ – evaluation of the selected n coefficients in points;

$\sum t_k$ – total estimation of n coefficients of "ideal" personality in balls;

$\bar{t}$ – n arithmetic mean of the estimates of the coefficients;

t_k – the highest number of points ($t_k=5$) for the ideal solution $T_{rel}=1$ for other options $T_{rel}<1$.

Formula (1) is used for equivalence of all functions and, therefore, coefficients. If the coefficients are not equivalent, in formula (1) we introduce the coefficient of weight of the coefficients (u):

$$P_{rel} = \frac{u_1 \cdot t_1 + u_2 \cdot t_2 + \dots + u_n \cdot t_n}{(u_1 + u_2 + \dots + u_n) \cdot t_k} \quad (2)$$

Consider the relative self-esteem of the level of self-government ($P_{(odn)}$) by the formula (1) on the conditional example, the company "N". Output data for this calculation are shown in tab. 3.

Table 3. Company N Output

№	Valuation functions of the self-management of a marine agency company	Designation of the coefficient of the corresponding function	Evaluation in points			
			Estimation of the analogue "ideal"	Self-esteem	Estimation of the nearest environment	Expert evaluation
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Adaptation to changes in legislation	$t_{1(CA)}$	5	4	4	4
2	Adaptation to change in the structure of seaports	$t_{2(OB)}$	5	4	3	3
3	The speed of implementation of structural / administrative changes	t_{3CK}	5	3	3	3
4	Speed of query processing	t_{4CM}	5	5	4	4
5	Compliance to structural hierarchy	t_{5CH}	5	5	4	4
6	Planning of working activities	t_{6CHP}	5	5	3	4

Continuation of the Table 3

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7	Monitoring the development of competition	t_{7CP}	5	4	4	4
8	Assessment of opportunities to diversify	t_{8CPPS}	5	4	4	5
9	Control over dynamics of sales	t_{9CP}	5	4	4	4
10	Monitoring level of expenses	t_{10CC}	5	4	4	3
11	Control over the level of profits	t_{11CO}	5	4	4	4
12	Control over the level of professional development of employees	t_{12CUB}	5	5	3	4
13	Staffing with skilled personnel	t_{13CUP}	5	4	3	3
14	The degree of congestion staff	t_{14COC}	5	4	3	3
Total			70	58	50	52
n arithmetic mean of the estimates of the coefficients			5	4.14	3.6	3.7

Source: own elaboration

It is important that the system of functions works, more functions maritime agency company owns higher P_{rel} ($0 \rightarrow 1$). Using formula (1) and data from tab. 3 define it P_{rel} in the following variants:

P_{rel} – relative self-assessment of the level of self-government maritime agency company, performed by the company itself "N";

$$P_{rel} = \frac{\bar{t}}{t_k} = \frac{4.14}{5} = 0.83$$

P_{rel}'' – relative self-assessment of the level of self-management by maritime agent company "N", which is carried out by the nearest environment;

$$P_{rel}'' = \frac{\bar{t}}{t_k} = \frac{3.6}{5} = 0.72$$

P_{rel}''' – relative self-assessment of the level of self-management by the marine agency company "N", which is carried out by experts

$$P_{rel}''' = \frac{\bar{t}}{t_k} = \frac{3.7}{5} = 0.74$$

It should be noted that not all features presented in tab. 3 are equivalent. For example, the greatest advantage can be given and enter the value of weights (u) only by the following four coefficients,

$$t_{1(CP)} \cdot 0.2, t_{2(CO)} \cdot 0.3, t_{10(CK)} \cdot 0.25, t_{11(CA)} \cdot 0.2$$

Then, relative assessment of level of self-management by the sea agency company, which is carried out by the company itself, is determined by the following formula (2)

$$P_{rel} = \frac{u_1 \cdot t_1 + u_2 \cdot t_2 + \dots + u_{10} \cdot t_{10} + u_{11} \cdot t_{11}}{(u_1 + u_2 + \dots + u_{10} + u_{11}) \cdot t_k} =$$

$$(2) = \frac{0.2 \cdot 4 + 0.3 \cdot 4 + 0.25 \cdot 4 + 0.2 \cdot 4}{(0.2 + 0.3 + 0.25 + 0.2) \cdot 5} = \frac{3.8}{4.75} = 0.8$$

Also, a relative assessment of the level of management of company "N", which is carried out by immediate environment, is determined by formula

$$P_{rel} = \frac{u_1 \cdot t_1 + u_2 \cdot t_2 + \dots + u_{10} \cdot t_{10} + u_{11} \cdot t_{11}}{(u_1 + u_2 + \dots + u_{10} + u_{11}) \cdot t_k} =$$

$$= \frac{0.2 \cdot 4 + 0.3 \cdot 3 + 0.25 \cdot 3 + 0.2 \cdot 4}{(0.2 + 0.3 + 0.25 + 0.2) \cdot 5} = \frac{3.25}{4.75} = 0.68$$

And lastly, the calculation is based on the use of expert estimates

$$P_{rel} = \frac{u_1 \cdot t_1 + u_2 \cdot t_2 + \dots + u_{10} \cdot t_{10} + u_{11} \cdot t_{11}}{(u_1 + u_2 + \dots + u_{10} + u_{11}) \cdot t_k} =$$

$$= \frac{0.2 \cdot 4 + 0.3 \cdot 3 + 0.25 \cdot 3 + 0.2 \cdot 4}{(0.2 + 0.3 + 0.25 + 0.2) \cdot 5} = \frac{3.25}{4.75} = 0.68$$

Assessment of the level of self-government is carried out by comparing the estimated coefficients with the corresponding coefficients of the analogue - the "ideal" company. Depending on the results of the comparison, the company may be attributed to:

- a self-employed company, if each of the values selected for the comparison of coefficients, deviates to the worst side by no more than 10% of the values of the corresponding coefficients of the analogue;
- inferior to a more influential company if each of the values selected for the comparison of coefficients is rejected by more than 10% to the worst of the values of the corresponding.

In case when deviation of values of individual key factors of rated company "N" exceeds 10% for "worse side", but no more than 15%, while others exceed corresponding coefficients of the analogue for "better side", then the estimated stage of the estimation (l_i). The calculation is performed on the main coefficients of comparability:

a) for coefficients, increase of which increases the level of self-management company "N"

$$l_i = t_i \div t_{i1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (3)$$

where t_i – absolute value i-th the estimated coefficient of the person being assessed;

t_{i1} – absolute value i-th coefficient of the analogue;

n – the number of fixed coefficients

b) for coefficients, increase of which reduces the level of self-management company "N"

$$l_i = t_i \div t_{i1} \quad (4)$$

The generalized coefficient of degree of conformity of the evaluated company "N" higher the coefficient of the analogue (t_{gen}) calculated by formula (with $t_{gen} \rightarrow$):

$$t_{\text{gen}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n I_i \quad (5)$$

During that t_{y_3} may be less than one (the level of self-government by company "N" does not correspond to the analogue).

As an example, we consider the calculation of the estimate t_{gen} company "N" on the basis of the deviation of value of main self-esteem coefficients. Using formula (3), we obtain following value of coefficients of level of self-esteem company "N":

$$\begin{aligned} t_{1(\text{CP})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; & t_{2(\text{CO})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; \\ t_{3(\text{C06})} &= 3 \div 5 = 0.6; & t_{4(\text{CM})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; \\ t_{5(\text{CH})} &= 5 \div 5 = 1; & t_{6(\text{CHP})} &= 5 \div 5 = 1; \\ t_{7(\text{CPOS})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; & t_{8(\text{CP})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; \\ t_{9(\text{CC})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; & t_{10(\text{CK})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; \\ t_{11(\text{CA})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; & t_{12(\text{CUB})} &= 5 \div 5 = 1; \\ t_{13(\text{CUP})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8; & t_{14(\text{COC})} &= 4 \div 5 = 0.8. \end{aligned}$$

The generalized coefficient according to the degree of conformity of the evaluated company "N" – to the "ideal" value – the higher coefficient of analogue t_{gen} tends to 1 and is calculated by the formula (5):

$$\begin{aligned} t_{\text{gen}} &= \frac{0.8+0.8+0.6+0.8+1+0.6+0.8+0.8+0.8+0.8+1+0.8+0.8}{14} = \\ &= \frac{13.16}{14} = 0.94 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, with $t_{\text{gen}} \rightarrow 1$ its actual value is equal to 0.94, namely, the level of the rated company "N" corresponds to the analogue.

Thus, we can take any company's agent shipping vessels, and evaluate the condition and status of maritime agency companies covering larger segments of the maritime agency's vessels, to maintain a fairly accurate result and relying on it, most company executives can develop or adjust their current development strategy and the company's work. At the

moment, this is a rather simple task due to the fact that when assessing / self-assessing it is not necessary to be passionate about evaluating your own company and making it a complete description, and then trusting assessment to develop a strategy. Most executives cannot withstand the passage of the first stage, considering their company as an ideal model, or as the least successful and promising, it is for this purpose attracted by external experts. They conduct not only evaluation but also can develop several strategies that will be tailored specifically to this company, taking into account all its features and objectives, as well as several of such companies can provide control over the implementation of the strategy developed and its changes throughout the implementation period.

Conclusions

Ukraine is a coastal state, for which the maritime economic complex plays an important economic role. Without organization of interaction of all its parts, economic development of any country is impossible. That is why development of maritime agency companies, as largest intermediaries of almost all participants of multimodal and regular transportation, is very important for the entire maritime-economic complex of the country. The developed method allows to evaluate and correct position of each maritime agency company separately and to see picture in general. From development of companies this significant part of work depends on the country's presentation to international carriers, principals, ship-owners and other third-party companies that have linked their business / work / transportation to that country. The advantage of this method is ability to conduct self-assessment without involvement of third parties, but in this case, the responsibility for results and their relevance to the real picture of market lies entirely with employee who conducted evaluation and depends on his view of a particular company, which is not always an impartial look.

Abstract

The article investigates activity maritime agents both in Ukraine and around the world. The main legal acts that determine the form and content of such relations marine agent with third parties and the principal, as well as set the volume of legal sides of the agency agreement. Were considered international and national agency organization. In recent years there has been a significant reduction in the level of the service sector of maritime transport. It is caused not so much an increase in tariffs and reduction of traffic in the Ukraine as a redistribution of "cargo" markets, and hence the transition of principals to other agents. Therefore, it becomes necessary to consider the activities of the marine agent, consider their rights, responsibilities and identify possible trends. Conduct a research-action, aimed at analyzing the situation and improve the operations of port infrastructure and content of the work is to protect the interests of the ship-owner (charterer) in collaboration with the port authorities, local authorities, other business entities. All this is caused not so much by the increase in tariffs and the decrease in the flow of goods in Ukraine as a redistribution of "freight" markets, and hence the transition of principals to other agents. In this regard, it becomes necessary to consider the activities of the maritime agent, consider its rights, functions and identify possible trends in the market of marine agency. Conduct scientific and practical research aimed at analyzing the status and improvement of each individual agency company, its place among its competitors.

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